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The Effect of TikTok on Students' Competence in English Vocabulary

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of TikTok videos on seventh-grade students' competence in English vocabulary. Vocabulary is a crucial component of language proficiency, influencing students' ability to read, write, listen, and speak effectively. However, many students struggle with vocabulary mastery, which impedes their overall language development. This research employed a quantitative approach, utilizing pre-tests and post-tests to measure changes in vocabulary competence after treatment with TikTok videos. The results showed a significant improvement in students' vocabulary comprehension, as reflected by higher post-test scores compared to pre-test scores. Statistical analysis, including paired t-tests, confirmed that the use of TikTok as a learning medium positively influenced students' vocabulary mastery. Additionally, students reported increased engagement during the learning process. These findings suggest that integrating TikTok videos into English language instruction can enhance students' vocabulary acquisition, making learning more interactive and enjoyable. This study concludes that TikTok is an effective educational tool for improving vocabulary skills and fostering student enthusiasm for language learning.

Keywords: TikTok, Student Competence, English Vocabulary, Language Learning, Educational Media

Abstrak

Penelitian ini menyelidiki pengaruh video TikTok terhadap kompetensi kosakata bahasa Inggris siswa kelas tujuh. Kosakata merupakan komponen penting dalam kemahiran berbahasa, yang memengaruhi kemampuan siswa dalam membaca, menulis, mendengarkan, dan berbicara secara efektif. Namun, banyak siswa yang kesulitan dalam penguasaan kosakata, yang menghambat perkembangan bahasa mereka secara keseluruhan. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif, dengan menerapkan pre-test dan post-test untuk mengukur perubahan dalam kompetensi kosakata setelah perlakuan dengan video TikTok. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan adanya peningkatan signifikan dalam pemahaman kosakata siswa, yang tercermin dari skor post-test yang lebih tinggi dibandingkan dengan pre-test. Analisis statistik, termasuk uji-t berpasangan, mengonfirmasi bahwa penggunaan TikTok sebagai media pembelajaran berdampak positif terhadap penguasaan kosakata siswa. Selain itu, siswa melaporkan peningkatan keterlibatan selama proses pembelajaran. Temuan ini menunjukkan bahwa mengintegrasikan video TikTok dalam pengajaran bahasa Inggris dapat meningkatkan penguasaan kosakata siswa, menjadikan pembelajaran lebih interaktif dan menyenangkan. Penelitian ini menyimpulkan bahwa TikTok adalah alat pendidikan yang efektif untuk meningkatkan kemampuan kosakata dan mendorong antusiasme siswa dalam pembelajaran bahasa.

Kata kunci: TikTok, Kompetensi Siswa, Kosakata Bahasa Inggris, Pembelajaran Bahasa, Media Pendidikan

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INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is crucial everywhere, for example, mastering adequate vocabulary can help students to develop four skills (reading, listening, writing, and speaking). According to Sondakh & Sya (2022), these four skills are separate from each other, but they are related to each other and can even be combined with each other. Research by Amirzai (2021) further supports this claim, emphasizing that a

strong vocabulary foundation is essential for success in language comprehension and communication. The richer the vocabulary you have, the greater the chances of becoming proficient in the language. However, if students do not master vocabulary, they will find it difficult to understand conversations and reading in English. Furthermore, they will find it difficult to communicate verbally and in writing in English (Sa'd & Rajabi, 2018). Therefore, mastering vocabulary is the most important thing in order to have good English language skills.

Vocabulary is the collection of words that exist in a given language. In the context of English, vocabulary includes all the words used in the language, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, phrases, and idioms. English vocabulary consists of different levels, from basic vocabulary to advanced vocabulary. According to Rachmawati (2017), vocabulary plays an important role in learning English at both basic and advanced levels. This includes words used in everyday situations, at work, in academic settings, and in various other social contexts. The ability to expand one's English vocabulary can be improved in a number of ways, including by reading regularly, writing, listening to different types of audio material, watching English-language films or television programmes, and taking part in conversations or discussions in English. Learners need to understand how to learn vocabulary and how to monitor their progress. The common difficulties students face in learning English vocabulary can vary from memorisation problems to a lack of practice in relevant contexts. According to Sucandra et al. (2022), the problem of students' limited vocabulary needs to be addressed effectively as it is important for English language learning. In order to increase students' vocabulary by looking at technological developments, students need digitally based learning media. Students' vocabulary knowledge can be improved by using applications, multimedia, games, diaries, and journals, and social activities using English (Holidazia & Rodliyah, 2020).

The emergence of digital technology and social media platforms has changed the landscape of education and language learning. One of the most popular platforms is TikTok, a short-form video sharing application, which has gained immense popularity, especially among young people. According to Hanim (2021), TikTok is the fastest growing application, the seventh most downloaded application in the last decade, and one of the most famous applications in the world. It has hundreds of millions of customers, many of whom are children and secondary school students. This platform provides a unique and engaging way to create and share short videos with a global audience. In an educational context, the use of TikTok has shown significant potential, especially in improving vocabulary mastery among students. As noted by Rama, Hamdani, and Prihatini (2023), watching videos can help students learn vocabulary. Vocabulary is a fundamental aspect of language learning, and the use of technology such as TikTok offers an innovative approach to making vocabulary acquisition more effective and enjoyable. Incorporating TikTok into language learning provides a dynamic and immersive learning experience. This research aims to investigate the use of the TikTok application and its impact on students' vocabulary development.

Furthermore, the TikTok application is considered particularly suitable for junior high school students who often show limited interest in learning English vocabulary. Most of the students feel bored with their learning model, where the teacher only explains the material based on theory. Initial observations at SMPN 12 Gorontalo and found three problems, namely: 1) Students had difficulty in understanding the meaning of words and writing them because they were lazy and did not want to know the meaning of the words, so they only relied on dictionaries and did not remember the meaning or pay attention to how they were written. 2) Students cannot pronounce what they say correctly because they only read what is written and do not pay attention to their chanting style. In addition, teachers still use traditional methods or techniques in teaching, such as giving vocabulary lists and then asking students to memorise them, which makes students bored and uninterested in learning. Based on this explanation, the researcher aims to see if the use of the TikTok media application can be used as a media tool to improve students' vocabulary skills in the school.

METHOD

This research applies quantitative techniques by systematically measuring and quantifying variables. The numerical data that has been collected is examined using IBM SPSS 21. A quantitative approach is a type of approach that produces findings that can be obtained using statistical procedures or other measurements. In this quantitative technique uses numerical or statistical data analysis to test

data in order to test the hypothesis put forward and analyze certain populations or samples randomly using research data collection instruments.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. (Interval Pre-test)

No	Value Interval	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	19-28	1	4.0	4.0	4.0
2	29-38	2	8.0	8.0	12.0
3	39-48	1	4.0	4.0	16.0
4	49-58	8	32.0	32.0	48.0
5	59-68	6	24.0	24.0	72.0
6	69-78	6	24.0	24.0	96.0
7	79-88	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total		25	100.0	100.0	

Table 1. above shows that the students' vocabulary comprehension is still at a medium level, as can be seen from the pre-test results, where only 1 student answered the questions correctly and got the highest score, namely 79-88, with a valid percentage of 4.0%. Apart from that, there were 8 students who scored low, namely 49-58, with a valid percentage of 32.0%. Apart from that, there were several other students who got the lowest scores: 1 student with the lowest score of 19-28, 2 students with a score of 29-38, and 1 other student with a score of 39-48. Therefore, it can be concluded that the results of the pre-test data indicate that the majority of the students still lack vocabulary understanding.

Table 2 (Interval Posttest)

No	Value Interval	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	64-68	4	16.0	16.0	16.0
2	69-72	4	16.0	16.0	32.0
3	73-76	4	16.0	16.0	48.0
4	77-80	7	28.0	28.0	76.0
5	85-88	4	16.0	16.0	92.0
6	89-92	2	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total		25	100.0	100.0	

The post-test table 2. above, is divided into 7 classes, shows that 2 students got the highest score with a score of 89-92 with a percentage of 8.0%, while 4 students got the lowest score with a score of 4-68 with a percentage of 16.0%. Apart from that, there were 7 students who got a fair score with a score of 77-80 and a percentage of 28.0%. So, by looking at the table above, it can be seen that students' vocabulary understanding has improved rapidly because the students' post-test scores are higher than their pre-test scores.

Table 3. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pre-Test	.139	25	.200*	.929	25	.080
Post-Test	.166	25	.073	.945	25	.190

Based on the Table 3. above, it can be seen that the results of the SPSS version 21 programme in the column show that the pre-test and post-test data are normally distributed if $p > 0.05$. Based on the data above, the pre-test has a value of $0.080 > 0.05$, while the post-test has a value of $0.190 > 0.05$. Thus, it can be assumed that the calculation results of these two data are normally distributed.

Table 4. Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Pre-Test	58.3200	25	15.47234	3.09447
	Post-Test	78.0800	25	8.09280	1.61856

This output table 4. includes descriptive statistics from the two sample treatments, namely the pre-test and the post-test. The average pre-test score was 58.32, and the average post-test score was 78.08. The total number of participants who became research respondents was 25. The pre-test standard deviation value is 15.47, and the post-test standard deviation value is 8.09.

Apart from that, in order to assess the influence or not of the videos on the TikTok application on the students' learning outcomes related to their vocabulary knowledge, researchers must analyze the results of the paired sample T test, which is presented in output table 4.5 below:

Table 5. Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
Pair 1 Pre-Test- Post-Test	-19.76000	12.71246	2.54249	-25.00745	-14.51255	-7.772	24	.000

The most significant output is in Table 5. above, because it answers the question of whether or not the use of videos in the TikTok application affects students' vocabulary knowledge and learning outcomes in class 7B of SMPN 12 Gorontalo. However, before discussing how to interpret the data in the paired sample t-test result table above, researchers are first given information about how research hypotheses are formed and how decisions are made using the paired sample t-test.

In the criteria verification of this research used the significance level $\alpha = 0,05$. If the Value of sig.(2-tailed) <0.05 then H_0 was rejected and H_a is accepted otherwise. If the value of sig.(2-tailed) > 0.05 then H_0 was accepted and H_a is rejected. H_a = Videos on the TikTok application can effects students' vocabulary. H_0 = Videos on the TikTok application cannot effects students' vocabulary.

Discussion

This research aimed to examine the effect of TikTok videos on improving students' vocabulary comprehension. The results showed a significant improvement in the students' vocabulary skills after the treatment, highlighting the effectiveness of using TikTok as a teaching tool.

In the pre-test, students demonstrated a moderate level of vocabulary comprehension. The average pre-test score was low, with many students struggling to understand the questions due to a lack of vocabulary. The majority of students were unable to answer more than half of the questions correctly. This initial finding is consistent with the notion that limited vocabulary can hinder the comprehension of procedural texts, as students face difficulties in both interpreting the questions and selecting the correct answers. Despite these challenges, the students made an effort to respond, which indicated their willingness to engage, although their limited vocabulary was a clear barrier to achieving higher scores.

The treatment, which involved the use of TikTok videos as an educational tool, aimed to address these vocabulary gaps. The four meetings, each focusing on different procedural topics, encouraged active participation and engagement from the students. The students' enthusiasm increased as they were exposed to familiar and interesting topics, such as "How to make watermelon milk ice cream" and "How to make avocado juice." This engagement aligns with the findings of Abidah (2022), which noted that social media platforms like TikTok and Instagram can be both enjoyable and effective for learning vocabulary. In particular, the use of video-based content in a social media format kept the students motivated and focused on the material, enhancing their learning experience.

By the time the post-test was administered, there was a noticeable improvement in the students' vocabulary recognition. The post-test scores were significantly higher than the pre-test scores, indicating that the TikTok videos facilitated vocabulary acquisition. This improvement can be attributed to the engaging nature of the videos, which allowed students to connect new vocabulary with real-world contexts in a manner that was both interactive and entertaining. As students were exposed to various vocabulary words in the videos, they had the opportunity to see how these words were used in context, reinforcing their understanding and retention.

The results from the post-test further support this conclusion. The post-test scores revealed that many students had significantly improved their vocabulary comprehension. The highest score in the pre-test was 58.32, while the post-test score reached 78.08, demonstrating a substantial increase in students' vocabulary skills. This aligns with the findings by Rama, Hamdani, and Prihatini (2023), which suggest

that watching educational videos can help students learn vocabulary more effectively. Vocabulary is a fundamental aspect of language learning, and the use of technology such as TikTok offers an innovative approach to making vocabulary acquisition more effective and enjoyable. The improved post-test scores reflect not only an increase in vocabulary but also greater comprehension of procedural texts, as students were able to answer questions more accurately and with greater confidence.

Throughout the treatment phase, the students exhibited increasing enthusiasm, which was reflected in their active participation. In the final meeting, where students worked in groups and discussed topics through the TikTok videos provided, the level of engagement was high. The students collaborated well in groups, demonstrating their understanding of the vocabulary and content. This aligns with the idea that the use of social media in education can promote collaboration and interaction, fostering a more dynamic learning environment.

In addition to the improvements in vocabulary comprehension, students also became more confident in their ability to use the vocabulary in context. This suggests that TikTok videos, by providing context-rich learning experiences, helped students not only to learn new words but also to apply them in meaningful ways. As students engaged with the content, they were able to practice their vocabulary skills in a way that felt relevant and enjoyable, which likely contributed to their improved performance on the post-test.

The significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores demonstrates the effectiveness of the TikTok-based intervention. By utilizing videos in an educational context, students were able to acquire new vocabulary and enhance their understanding of procedural texts in a way that was both engaging and effective. This result supports the findings of previous research (Abidah, 2022), which suggests that social media platforms, including TikTok, can be powerful tools for improving vocabulary acquisition and comprehension.

CONCLUSION

The research findings focused on the impact of using videos on the TikTok application to teach vocabulary skills to seventh grade students. The study included a pre-test and a post-test to assess students' vocabulary achievement. The pre-test results showed that most of the students had an intermediate level of vocabulary comprehension, with only one student scoring at the highest level and many scoring at a low level. Following the treatment process, which involved watching TikTok videos on various topics, the students showed an improvement in their vocabulary skills on the post-test. The post-test results showed higher scores compared to the pre-test, suggesting that the use of the TikTok application had a positive impact on the students' vocabulary mastery. The data from the study were found to be normally distributed based on the results of the normality test. The paired t-test analysis showed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores, confirming the effectiveness of using TikTok videos in improving students' vocabulary knowledge. Overall, the use of TikTok as a teaching tool was found to increase students' engagement in learning English vocabulary, leading to improvements in their vocabulary skills. The study concluded that TikTok videos can be a useful tool for teachers to enhance vocabulary learning in the classroom.

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